

TIME-TEMPERATURE DEPENDENT TENSILE BEHAVIOR OF UNIDIRECTIONAL CFRP

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SUMMARY: We had observed that the tensile strength along the longitudinal direction of unidirectional CFRP under constant strain-rate (CSR) loading is highly time-temperature dependent. The trend of the inherently scattered strength data seemed to obey the time-temperature superposition principle with the shift factor for the matrix resin. In our previous paper [1], we proposed a prediction scheme of the master curve for the tensile strength of CFRP under CSR loading: we extended Rosen's analysis [2] for tensile failure of unidirectional fibrous composites with elastic matrix to CFRP with viscoelastic matrix. The predicted master curve for the tensile strength of CFRP captured the test data adequately. However, we used an assumed value 7.5 for Weibull shape parameter of fiber strength and the shear relaxation modulus of matrix resin which is obtained indirectly from the apparent tensile relaxation modulus of CFRP by use of the rule of mixtures.

In this paper, we carry out the tensile test under various constant strain rates and temperatures for two types of CFRP, the matrices of both of which are the same epoxy resin while the carbon fibers for one type are of low modulus and those for another type of high modulus. We construct the master curves of tensile CSR strength for two types of CFRP and predict these master curves using the Weibull shape parameter of each carbon fiber strength which is obtained experimentally and the shear relaxation modulus of matrix resin which is obtained directly by use of neat resin plate. For CFRP with carbon fibers of low modulus, the predicted master curve for failure captured the test results adequately over the entire range tested, while those of high modulus, the predicted master curve failed to capture the test results in the range of moderate to high temperature and long time to failure.

KEYWORDS: Unidirectional CFRP, Tensile Strength, Time-Temperature Dependence, Prediction of Strength

1. INTRODUCTION

The mechanical behavior of polymer resin exhibits time and temperature dependence, called viscoelastic behavior, not only above the glass-transition temperature T_g but also below T_g . Thus, it can be presumed that the fracture behavior of CFRP using polymer resin as matrix also depends on time and temperature even below T_g which is within the normal operating-temperature range.

We had observed that the tensile strength along the longitudinal direction of unidirectional CFRP under constant strain-rate (CSR) loading is highly time-temperature dependent. The trend of the inherently scattered strength data seemed to obey the time-temperature superposition principle with the shift factor for the matrix resin. In our previous paper [1], we proposed a prediction scheme of the master curve for the tensile strength of unidirectional CFRP under CSR loading: we extended Rosen's analysis [2] for tensile failure of unidirectional fibrous composites with elastic matrix to CFRP with viscoelastic matrix. The predicted master curve for the tensile strength of CFRP captured the test data adequately. However, we used an assumed value 7.5 for Weibull shape parameter of fiber strength and the shear relaxation modulus of matrix resin which is obtained indirectly from the apparent tensile

relaxation modulus of CFRP by use of the rule of mixtures.

In this paper, we carry out the tensile test under various constant strain rates and temperatures for two types of CFRP, the matrices of both of which are the same epoxy resin while the carbon fibers for one type are of low modulus and those for another type of high modulus. We construct the master curves of tensile CSR strength for two types of CFRP and predict these master curves using the Weibull shape parameter of each carbon fiber strength which is obtained experimentally and the shear relaxation modulus of matrix resin which is obtained directly by use of neat resin plate. For CFRP with carbon fibers of low modulus, the predicted master curve for failure captured the test results adequately over the entire range tested, while those of high modulus, the predicted master curve failed to capture the test results in the range of moderate to high temperature and long time to failure.

2. PREDICTION OF TENSILE STRENGTH OF CFRP

We proposed [1] a prediction scheme of the master curve of the tensile CSR strength for unidirectional CFRP which is an extension of Rosen's analysis [2] for tensile failure of unidirectional fibrous composites with elastic matrix to CFRP with viscoelastic matrix by making two modifications. First, we replaced the ineffective length with the recovery length over which the interfacial shear stress is uniform. Second, we substituted the value of shear relaxation modulus of polymer matrix at the time of failure for elastic shear modulus in Rosen's formula after the first modification. Finally, we defined the dimensionless CSR strength for unidirectional CFRP to be the ratio of σ_s of t_s and T , the strength at the time t_s under temperature T , to its glassy value σ_{sg} and found its expression:

$$\frac{\sigma_s(t_s, T)}{\sigma_{sg}} = \left[\frac{G_m(t_r, T)}{G_{mg}} \right]^{1/(2m)} \quad (1)$$

where m represents Weibull shape parameter of tensile strength of carbon fiber, $G_m(t_r, T)$ and G_{mg} are shear relaxation modulus of matrix resin at relaxation time t_r under temperature T , and its glassy value.

3. EXPERIMENT

3.1 Specimen

Two types of resin impregnated carbon fiber strand (CFRP strand) were employed as the tensile test specimen along the longitudinal direction of unidirectional CFRP. These two CFRP strands were produced by filament winding method, one consists of low modulus carbon fiber XN05 (NIPPON GRAPHITE FIBER) and a general purpose epoxy resin EPIKOTE[®] 828 (YUKA SHELL EPOXY). The other consists of high modulus carbon fiber XN50 (NIPPON GRAPHITE FIBER) and EPIKOTE[®] 828. The composition of epoxy resin and cure condition for the CFRP strand are shown in Table 1.

3.2 Tensile CSR tests for CFRP strand

The tensile CSR tests for CFRP strand along the fiber direction were carried out under four loading rates 0.01, 0.1, 1, 10 mm/min with corresponding strain rates of 5×10^{-5} , 10^{-4} , 10^{-3} , 10^{-2} /min and five temperature levels as indicated in the insert in Fig.6. Figure 1 shows the dimension of specimen and the grip end to which the fan-shaped ends of specimen are adhesively bonded. Figure 1 also includes the diagram for tensile-test setting consisting an Instron type testing machine with a temperature chamber. The tensile failure of all strands tested occurred within the central 70 mm region of the specimen with gage length 200mm. The tensile CSR strength $\sigma_s(t_s, T)$ of CFRP strand is defined by

$$\sigma_s(t_s, T) = P_{\max}(t_s, T) \frac{\rho}{t_e} \quad (2)$$

where P_{\max} , ρ , t_e are the maximum load [N] of the strand, the fiber density [g/m^3] and the tex of fiber strand [$(\text{g}/\text{m}) \times 10^6$], respectively. Therefore, the tensile strength of CFRP strand is calculated using the cross sectional area of carbon fiber bundle in the strand.

Table 1 Composition of epoxy resin and cure condition for CFRP strand

Composition		Weight ratio
Epoxy	Epikote 828	100
Hardener	Methyl himic anhidride	103.6
Cure accelerator	2-Ethyl-4-methylimidazol	1
Cure Condition		
70°C × 12h + 150°C × 4h + 190°C × 2h		

Fig.1 Strand specimen with end fitting and tensile test setting

3.3 Dynamic double cantilever test for epoxy resin

The dynamic double cantilever tests for neat epoxy resin were conducted at eleven angular velocities ω (0.01rad/sec to 50rad/sec) and thirty temperature levels listed in the insert in Fig.2. The length, width and thickness of specimen are 44.5, 6.4, and 1.6mm, respectively. The span is 36.5mm. We obtained the master curve of storage modulus for tension of neat epoxy resin.

3.4 Tensile CSR test for carbon mono filament

The CSR tests for XN05 and XN50 mono filaments were conducted under a loading rate 1mm/min

at room temperature. The gage length is 25mm. We obtained Weibull shape parameters of tensile strength for both mono filaments.

4. RESULTS AND OBSERVATIONS

4.1 Shear relaxation modulus for matrix resin

The storage modulus $E'(\omega, T)$ measured in 3.3 was converted to the tensile relaxation modulus $E_m(t_r, T)$ described using Christensen's approximate formula [3]:

$$E_m'(\omega, T) \Big|_{\omega=2/(\pi t_r)} \approx E_m(t_r, T) \quad \square \square \quad \square (3)$$

where t_r is the time for relaxation. In the left side of Fig.2, the dimensionless relaxation modulus $E_m(t_r, T)/E_{mg}$ defined by (3) is presented against logarithmic time scale for various temperatures. Shifting the curves other than the one for the reference temperature $T_0=50^\circ\text{C}$ horizontally so that they overlap on each other, we obtain a single smooth master curve against the reduced time t_r' as shown in the right hand side of this figure. A smooth curve thus obtained indicates the validity of the time-temperature superposition principle for the relaxation modulus. Here, we define the shift factor at a reference temperature T_0 for a response x by

$$a_{T_0;x}(T) = \frac{t_x}{t_x'} \quad \square(4)$$

where t_x, t_x' are the relevant physical time and the associated time, respectively. The shift factors for the relaxation modulus E_m obtained in the construction process of master curve are shown by open circles in Fig.3 where we set $x=r$ indicating the relaxation. The shift factors for the relaxation modulus are in good agreement with two Arrhenius equations with $\Delta H_1=113\text{kJ/mol}$ and $\Delta H_2=533\text{kJ/mol}$:

$$\log a_{T_0;r}(T) = \frac{\Delta H}{2.303R} \left(\frac{1}{T} - \frac{1}{T_0} \right) \quad \square(5)$$

where R is gas constant, $8.314 \times 10^{-3} [\text{kJ}/(\text{mol} \cdot \text{K})]$.

Fig.2 Master curve of relaxation modulus for matrix resin

Fig.3 Shift factor of relaxation modulus for matrix resin

If we regard elastic relation among Young's modulus, shear modulus and Poisson's ratio also for relaxation moduli and Poisson's ratio for epoxy at any instant and, in addition, Poisson's ratio is independent of temperature, the ratio of tensile moduli and that of shear moduli must be the same, Fig.4 exhibits the master curve for the ratio of shear moduli on logarithmic scale.

Fig.4 Dimensionless shear relaxation modulus for matrix resin

4.2 Weibull shape parameter for tensile strength of mono filament

The tensile CSR tests for mono filament were carried out as described in 3.4. Weibull plots of tensile strength measured for two type of mono filament, XN05 and XN50 are shown in Fig.5 which indicates Weibull shape parameter $m=5.5$ for XN05 and $m=5.6$ for XN50.

(a) XN05

(b) XN50

Fig.5 Weibull plot for failure probability F of mono filament

4.3 Master curve of tensile CSR strength for CFRP strand and its prediction

The tensile CSR tests for two types of CFRP strand, XN05/Ep828 and XN50/Ep828, were carried out at various strain rates and temperatures as described in 3.2. We plot the tensile strengths $\sigma_s(t_s, T)$ versus time to failure t_s , the time period from initial loading to maximum load, in logarithmic scale at various temperatures on the left side of Fig.6 where the scale of the left ordinate shows the strength σ_s in GPa while that on the right ordinate the dimensionless strength at the reference time t_{s0} and temperature T_0 . The trend of inherently scattered data was represented by a smooth dotted curve for each temperature. These curves are shifted toward the curve for the reference temperature $T_0=50^\circ\text{C}$ in the same manner as done in Fig.2 for the relaxation modulus and the smooth master curves were constructed as shown by dotted curves on the right side of Fig.6. Thus, we may claim that the time-temperature superposition principle holds also for the CSR strengths of CFRP strand, XN05/Ep828 and XN50/Ep828.

The solid curves on the right side of Fig.6 refers to the dimensionless strength $\sigma_s(t_s', T_0)/\sigma_{sg}$ evaluated from (1) using the dimensionless shear modulus in Fig.4 and Weibull shape parameters in Fig.5. The master curve for tensile CSR strength of XN05/Ep828 predicted by the proposed method

captured the test data adequately over the entire range tested. However, the predicted CSR strength of XN50/Ep828 does not agree with test data in the range of long time to failure and high temperature. Since the tensile modulus of carbon fiber XN50 is extremely higher than that for epoxy resin, CFRP strand, XN50/Ep828, may be regarded as a bundle of carbon fiber XN50 and violates the basic assumptions in Rosen's model; the effect of matrix resin on the strength of CFRP is negligible and, therefore, the tensile CSR strength of XN50/Ep828 scarcely depends on time and temperature.

(a) XN05/EP828

(b) XN50/EP828

Fig.6 Master curve of tensile CSR strength for CFRP strand

5. CONCLUSION

We carried out the tensile test under various constant strain rates and temperatures for two types of CFRP, the matrices of both of which were the same epoxy resin Epikote828 while the carbon fibers for one were of low modulus XN05 and those for another type of high modulus XN50. We constructed the master curves of tensile CSR strength for two types of CFRP and predicted these master curves using the Weibull shape parameter of each carbon fiber strength which was obtained experimentally and the shear relaxation modulus of matrix resin which was obtained directly by use of

neat resin plate. For CFRP with carbon fibers of low modulus, the predicted master curve for failure captured the test results adequately over the entire range tested, while those of high modulus, the predicted master curve failed to capture the test results in the range of moderate to high temperature and long time to failure.

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